

Review on the major wheat rusts (yellow, Stem and leaf rust) diseases of wheat in different parts of the world

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Abstract

Wheat rusts caused by *Puccinia* spp. are among the major/biotic constraints of wheat production all over the world, including in Ethiopia. Now a day's different stem rust, yellow rust and also leaf rust races have evolved and threaten wheat production worldwide across all wheat belt areas, among which east Africa, Ethiopia is found the most vulnerable. In view of the above facts, the present investigation was carried out to know the current status of yellow, stem and leaf rust all over the world and in Africa mainly in east Africa, Ethiopia.

1. Introduction

The most important diseases of wheat that significantly reduce wheat production are the rusts (yellow, stem and leaf rusts). The rusts of wheat are among the most widely spread pathogens that can be found in most areas of the world where wheat is grown. They are spread in the form of clonally produced dikaryotic uredospore's, which can be dispersed by wind for thousands of kilometers from initial infection sites across different areas even from continent to continent. Epidemics of wheat rusts can occur on a continental scale due to the widespread dispersal of uredospore (Khan *et al.*, 2013).

Wheat rust fungi are highly specific obligate parasites. Rust populations can be characterized by distribution of races and the frequencies of virulence against specific rust resistance genes on a defined set of wheat differential hosts (Khan *et al.*, 2013). Wheat leaf, stripe and stem rusts have devastating role in reducing crop yield resulting in socio-economic instability many times across the world. The semi-dwarf wheat varieties with race specific resistance could not survive longer due to the evolution of new rust races (Rehman *et al.*, 2013).

Stripe rust probably occurred long before wheat was grown for food, the disease was first described by Gaddin Europe in 1777 and it has been reported in more than 60 countries on all continents except Antarctica (Chen, 2005). Stripe rust prevalence changes from year to year and from place to place, depending on climatic conditions and variety grown (Teklay Abebe *et al.*, 2013). Major stripe rust (*Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. *tritici*) epidemics occurred in Ethiopia in 1970's, 1988, 2010 (Nazari, 2011). In the Bale highlands, wheat is produced twice a year favoring the continuous perpetuation of the three rust pathogens year-round. Rust monitoring conducted over 1996 to 2000, and surveys indicated that the disease is more important, endemic and severe in the main season (August to December) than in short season (March to July) (Dereje Hailu and Chemedda Fininsa, 2009). The development of yellow rust epidemics, in addition to favorable weather factors, depends on the level of cultivar susceptibility, which affects the disease occurrence and its progress, cropping systems and management practices (Dereje Hailu and Chemedda Fininsa, 2009). This situation provides the pathogen not only with a substrate both in area and time, but also results in successive evolution of pathotype lineages and/or new races of the pathogen (Kebede Tadesse *et al.*, 2011).

In 2010 more than 400,000 ha of wheat were affected by yellow rust which led to serious losses, though difficult to measure. The epidemic covered almost all wheat growing regions in the country except Tigray Regional state (Nazari, 2011). Most of the commercial bread wheat cultivars were susceptible to yellow rust (Nazari, 2011).

Stem rust caused by *Puccinia graminis* f. sp. *tritici* is amongst the biotic factors which can cause up to 100% yield loss in Ethiopia if susceptible cultivars are grown and epidemic occurs (Efrem Bechere *et al.*, 2000). Stem rust isolates with virulence to Sr9e and Sr13 were first reported in Ethiopia in 1988 and 1989, respectively, (Mengistu Hulluka *et al.*, 1991). The East African highlands are a known “hot-spot” for the evolution and survival of new rust races (Singh *et al.*, 2008). A total of nine races were identified, which include TTKSK, TTKTF, TTKTK, JRCQC, TKTTF, TTKSC, TRTTF, SRKSC and RRKSF (Endale Hailu *et al.*, 2015). Race TTKSK was dominant and widely distributed in the Oromia and Amhara regions with 52% frequency while; it was not found in Tigray region (Endale Hailu *et al.*, 2015). The most virulent and new race, TKTTF which causes localized stem rust epidemic in Bale and Arsi was predominantly distributed in Oromia region with 36.4% frequency (Endale Hailu *et al.*, 2015).

Leaf rust (*Puccinia triticina* Eriks.) of wheat is the most common and widely distributed of all the cereal rusts (Kolmer, 1996) and accounts for major yield losses every year (Kolmer *et al.* 2003). In Ethiopia leaf rust is not a devastating disease compared to the two rusts (yellow rust and stem rust) but, it has the potential to constrain wheat production in South-eastern parts of Ethiopia (Daniel Kasa *et al.*, 2015). Leaf rust was observed in the mid-altitude and in the lowland wheat producing areas of East Hararge (Samuel Tegene *et al.*, 2014). In northern parts of Ethiopia, Tigray, the severity and incidence of leaf rust reached 100% on susceptible wheat varieties during suitable environmental condition for leaf rust development (Teklay Abebe *et al.*, 2015).

The three rusts (stem, stripe and leaf rusts of wheat) are known to occur all over the world, in areas where wheat is produced but their damage depends on the environmental conditions and the types of cultivars grown. Infection can occur anytime from the one-leaf stage to plant maturity provided plants are still green (Chen, 2005). The discovery of genetic resistance by Biffen (1905), physiological specialization in the rust by Stakman and Levine (1992), and the gene for gene interaction theory by Flor (1959), the use of race specific types of resistance has been dominating rust resistance in wheat improvement programs. However, resistance based on single race-specific genes often becomes ineffective within few years producing “boom and bust” cycles in wheat production. The “bust” cycles (when rust resistance has been overcome) are caused by pathogens mutating to acquire virulence, virulent races migrating into a new region or the appearance of races favored by selection pressure from the existing pathogen population (Zhengi, 2002).

2. Literature review

2.1 Origin and distribution of rusts

2.1.1 Stem rust (*Puccinia graminis* f.sp. *tritici*)

Stem rust has been a serious disease of wheat, barley, oat and rye, as well as various important grasses including timothy, tall fescue and perennial ryegrasses (Kurt J. *et al.*, 2005). One hundred wheat stem rust samples were collected in 2013 cropping season in the Oromia, Amhara and Tigray region resulting in identification of nine races: TTKSK (Ug99), TTKTF, TTKTK, JRCQC, TKTTF, TTKSC, TRTTF, SRKSC and RRKSF (Endale Hailu *et al.*, 2015).

Race Ug99 of the fungus *Puccinia graminis tritici* that causes stem or black rust disease on wheat was first detected in Uganda in 1998 (Singh *et al.*, 2006). Seven races belonging to the Ug99 lineage are now known and have spread to various wheat growing countries in the eastern African highlands, as well as Zimbabwe, South Africa, Sudan, Yemen, and Iran (Singh *et al.*, 2011). Because of the susceptibility of 90% of the wheat varieties grown world-wide, the Ug99 group of races was recognized as a major threat to wheat production and food security (Singh *et al.*, 2011). Its spread, either wind-mediated or human-aided, to other countries in Africa, Asia, and beyond is evident (Singh *et al.*, 2011).

2.1.2 Leaf rust (*Puccinia triticina*)

The evolutionary history of the obligate rust pathogen on wheat, *Puccinia triticina*, is correlated with adaptation to hosts with different ploidy levels (Liu *et al.*, 2013). Phylogenetic analyses (parsimony, Bayesian, maximum likelihood) showed the clear initial divergence of *P. triticina* isolates collected from *Aegilops speltoides* (the likely B genome donor of modern wheat) in Israel from the other isolates that were collected from tetraploid (AB genomes) durum wheat and hexaploid (ABD genomes) common wheat (Liu *et al.*, 2013). Coalescence-based genealogy samplers also indicated that *P. triticina* on *A. speltoides*, diverged initially, followed by *P. triticina* isolates from durum wheat in Ethiopia and then by isolates from common wheat (Liu *et al.*, 2013). Isolates of *P. triticina* found worldwide on cultivated durum wheat were the most recently coalesced and formed a clade nested within the isolates from common wheat (Liu *et al.*, 2013). By a relative time scale, the divergence of *P. triticina* as delimited by host specificity appears very recent. Significant reciprocal gene flow between isolates from common wheat and isolates from durum wheat that are found worldwide was detected, in addition to gene flow from isolates on common wheat to isolates on durum wheat in Ethiopia (Liu *et al.*, 2013).

2.1.3 Yellow rust/stripe rust (*Puccinia striiformis* Westend)

Yellow/stripe rust which is caused by *Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. *tritici*. However, the worldwide population structure and the center of origin of the pathogen were still unknown (Justesen *et al.*, 2014). Analyses of linkage disequilibrium and

genotypic diversity indicated a strong regional heterogeneity in levels of recombination, with clear signatures of recombination in the Himalayan (Nepal and Pakistan) and near-Himalayan regions (China), and a predominant clonal population structure in other regions (Justesen et al., 2014). The higher genotypic diversity, recombinant population structure and high sexual reproduction ability in the Himalayan and neighboring regions suggests this area as the putative center of origin of *Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. *tritici* (PST) (Justesen et al., 2014). Justesen et al (2014) used clustering methods and approximate Bayesian computation (ABC) to compare different competing scenarios describing ancestral relationship among ancestral populations and more recently founded populations. Their analyses confirmed that the Middle East-East Africa as the most likely source of newly spreading, high- temperature-adapted strains; Europe as the source of South American, North American and Australian populations; and Mediterranean-Central Asian populations as the origin of South African populations (Justesen et al., 2014). The existence of a high genotypic diversity, a high sexual ability as well as the independent maintenance of strongly differentiated populations in the Himalayan region pinpoint this region as the possible centre of origin of PST (Sajid, 2013).

2.1.4 Common signs and symptoms of wheat rusts

Stripe/yellow rust appears as a mass of yellow to orange urediniospores erupting from pustules arranged in long, narrow stripes on leaves (usually between veins), leaf sheaths, glumes and awns on susceptible plants. Resistant wheat cultivars are characterized by various infection types from no visual symptoms to small hypersensitive flecks to uredinia surrounded by chlorosis or necrosis with restricted urediniospore production. On seedlings, uredinia produced by the infection of a single urediniospore are not confined by leaf veins, but progressively emerge from the infection site in all directions, potentially covering the entire leaf surface (Chen et al., 2014).

The symptoms of stem rust on wheat appear as elliptical blisters or pustules, known as uredia that develop parallel with the long axis of the stem, leaf, or leaf sheath. Blisters may also appear on the neck and glumes of the wheat spike. The epidermis covering the pustules is later ruptured irregularly and pushed back, revealing a powdery mass of brick red-colored uredospores. The uredia vary in size from 1 to 3 millimetres wide by 10 millimetres long. Later in the season, as the plant approaches maturity, the pustules turn black as the fungus produces teliospores instead of uredospores and uredia are transformed into black telia. Sometimes telia may develop independently of uredia. Uredia and telia may exist on wheat plants in such great numbers that large parts of the plant appear to be covered with the ruptured areas, which are filled with the rust red uredospores, the black teliospores, or both. On barberry, the symptoms of stem rust appear as yellowish to orange-colored spots primarily on the leaves. Within the spots, and in leaves generally on the upper side, appear a few minute, orange-colored bodies, the spermagonia, usually bearing a small droplet of liquid or nectar. Beneath the spermagonia, and occasionally next to them, groups of orange-yellow horn- or cup-like aecia appear (Agrios, 2005).

Leaf rust is generally found on leaves but may also infect glumes and awns. Symptoms begin as small circular to oval yellow spots on infected tissue of the upper leaf surface. As the disease progresses, the spots develop into orange-colored pustules that may be surrounded by a yellow halo. The pustules produce a large number of spores that are easily dislodged from the pustule, resulting in an “orange dust” on the leaf surface or on clothes, hands, and equipment. As the disease progresses, black spores may be produced, resulting in a mixture of orange and black lesions on the same leaf. Leaf rust is characterized by red pustules or uredinia scattered on infected leaves (Fetch et al., 2011).

Table 1. The most distinguishing features of the three wheat rusts

Pustule character	Stripe rust	Leaf rust	Stem rust
Color	✓ Yellow	✓ Orange brown	✓ Reddish brown
Shape	✓ Small, circular, densely packed on seedling leaves and in yellow stripes running along the leaf in older plants	✓ Circular to oval in random pattern on leaf	✓ Oval to elongated with conspicuously tattered edges, random pattern on leaf
Location on plant	✓ Chiefly on upper surface of leaf but also on leaf sheaths, awns and inside of glumes (head infection)	✓ Chiefly on upper surface of leaf and leaf sheaths	✓ On both sides of leaf, on leaf sheaths, stems and outside of head

2.2 Host ranges of rusts

Puccinia striiformis (Pst) has its hosts in the cereal group; wheat and barley are the principal hosts. Several wild grasses can harbor stripe rust pathogenic to wheat and barley but their role in the epidemiology of stripe rust differs from area to area (Roelfs & Bushnell, 1985). Additionally barberry serves as host for yellow/ stripe rusts (Hansen *et al.*, 2013). Pst mainly infects common wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.), durum wheat (*T. turgidum* var. durum L.), cultivated emmer wheat (*T. dicoccum* Schrank), wild emmer wheat (*T. dicoccoides* Korn) and triticale (*Tritico secale*). It can infect certain cultivated barleys (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) and rye (*Secale cereale* L.) but generally does not cause severe epidemics. In addition, it may infect naturalized and improved pasture grass species, such as *Elymus canadensis* L., *Leymus secalinus* Hochst, *Agropyron* spp. *Garetn*, *Hordeum* spp. L., *Phalaris* spp. L and *Bromus unioloides* Kunth. Pycnial/aecial (alternative) hosts: Barberry (*Berberis chinensis*, *B. koreana*, *B. holstii*, *B. vulgaris*, *B. shensiana*, *B. potaninii*, *B. dolichobotrys*, *B. heteropoda*, etc.) and Oregon grape (*Mahonia aquifolium*) (Chen *et al.*, 2014).

Hosts for leaf rust (*Puccinia triticina* Eriks) are common wheat (*Triticum aestivum*.L), durum wheat (*T. turgidum* L.var durum), cultivated emmer wheat (*T.dicoccon*), wild emmer wheat(*T.dicoccoides*), *Aegilops speltoides*, goat grass (*Ae.cylindrica*) and Triticale (*X.triticosecale*) and the alternate host for leaf rust of wheat is *Thalictrum speciosissimum* (*T.flavum Glaucum*) and *Isopyrum fumaroides* (Melvin *et al.*, 2008).

Puccinia graminis, causal agent of stem rust on wheat, barley, and oat, has a complex heteroecious life cycle with species in the Triticeae being telial/uredinial stage primary hosts (Leonard and Szabo, 2005). *Berberis vulgaris* can serve as alternate hosts for stem rust (Roelfs *et al.*,1992). *Lolium temulentum* and *Setaria pumila* were identified to be secondary hosts for wheat stem rust (CIMMYT, 2000).

2. 3 Diseases development

The presence of a pathogen against a particular plant will generally not cause serious diseases unless the environmental conditions are favorable. The following conditions are the requirement for wheat rust diseases development.

Table 2. Environmental conditions required for wheat rusts

Stage	Temperature (°c)			Light	Free water
	Minimum	Optimum	Maximum		
Leaf rust					
Germination	2	20	30	Low	Essential
Apressorium	-	15-20	-	Non	Essential
Penetration	10	20	30	No effect	Essential
Growth	2	25	35	High	Non
Sporulation	10	25	35	High	Non
Stem rust					
Germination	2	15-24	30	Low	Essential
Apressorium	-	16-27	-	Non	Essential
Penetration	15	29	35	High	Essential
Growth	5	30	40	High	Non
Sporulation	15	30	40	High	Non
Yellow rust					
Germination	0	9-13	23	Low	Essential
Apressorium	-	-	Not formed	Non	Essential
Penetration	2	8-13	23	Low	Essential
Growth	3	12-15	20	High	Non
Sporulation	5	12-15	20	High	Non

Source: (Roelfs *et al.*, 1992).

2.4 Yield losses caused by rusts

Rust symptoms are confusing for farmers due to lack of agricultural pest information. Even though the farmers are capable of controlling wheat rusts through chemical management they are not effective in overcoming the disease problem due to unwise use and incorrect rate of fungicides. Yield losses inflicted by rusts depend on the level of resistance and susceptibility of varieties for rusts and also the climatic condition of the production season in a given area.

In Pakistan yield loss assessment was done and 5.77% yield loss was recorded on the resistance variety (Inquilab-91). Whereas Morocco, proved to be the most susceptible wheat variety to yellow rust with maximum yield deficit to the tune of 39.79% in Pakistan (Bashir *et al.*, 2007). Yield losses ranged between 1.96 % in the wheat cultivar Gemmeiza 7 to 8.21 % in the wheat cultivar Misr 1 was recorded due to stem rust in Egypt (Mamdouh *et al.*, 2013).

In Ethiopia yellow rust yield loss was assessed on superimposed trials of wheat and the result from the assessment indicated that Grain yield losses of 47.2% and 32% were observed in the worst scenario in north Shewa and in east Gojam zones, respectively (Landuber Wendale *et al.*, 2016). Grain yield loss was lowest (28%) for south Gondar zone (Landuber Wendale *et al.*, 2016).

Yield losses due to stem rust reached 29% on variety Sirbo and 21.1% on Maddawalabu in 2005 at Agarfa. In 2006, grain yield losses were 25.7% on Sirbo and 18.6% on Maddawalabu. In 2006, the disease reduced grain yield by 22.1% on Sirbo and 18.1% on Maddawalabu (Kebede Tadesse *et al.*, 2010). The epidemic, which developed in December 1993 and spread rapidly throughout the regions where Enkoy was grown, reduced Enkoy yields by 65 to 100 percent (Shank 1994). In the highland wheat areas, yields were reduced by an estimated 42 percent by the epidemic. Total susceptibility and 100 percent yield loss due to stem rust was noted in a fungicide experiment conducted on Enkoy at Kulumsa Agricultural Research Center, in the following year (Ayele Badebo and Temesgen Kebede 1996).

Yield losses due to leaf rust is significant and estimated to reach 30– 70% or even greater on susceptible varieties depending on the environmental condition and inoculum pressure (Murray *et al.*, 1994). In Ethiopia even if leaf rust has limited effect on wheat production, it resulted in 75% yield loss during epidemic condition (Teklay Abebe, 2015).

2.5 Rust management

2.5.1 Cultural

No single practice is effective under all conditions but using a series of cultural practices greatly enhances the existing resistances. Removing the green bridge with tillage or herbicides is an effective control measure for epidemics that would result from endogenous inoculums, gene deployment (which can be obtained by a grower if more than one cultivar are used that differ in resistance and from those grown by immediate neighbors), control of timing and frequency and amount of irrigation and fertilization applications (Roelfs *et al.*, 1992). Practices such as changing planting dates, destroying alternate host plants, using multi-lines or varietal mixtures are also used in rust management (Wiik, 2009).

2.5.2 Chemical

Foliar fungicides can effectively control stripe rust. Applied when the crop is at the boot stage of development, the fungicides should provide protection for the upper leaves that contribute most of the energy used to produce grain. Products belonging to the strobilurin class of fungicides (Headline, Quadris) provide excellent activity against stripe rust but are most effective when applied before infection. If stripe rust is already present in a field at the time of application, it is better to use products belonging to the triazole class of fungicides (Folicur, Prosaro, Tilt) or premixes of the two classes (Quilt, Stratego, Twinline). The triazole class of fungicide is generally considered to have stronger curative activity. Four active ingredients are currently registered as seed treatments for the control of stripe rust in seedlings: flutriafol, triadimenol, triticonazole and fluquinconazole (Murray *et al.*, 2005). Nativo 300 SC (trifloxystrobin 100 g L⁻¹ + tebuconazole 200 g L⁻¹) and Prosaro 250 EC (prothioconazole 125 g L⁻¹ + tebuconazole 125 g L⁻¹) applied at the rate of 1.0 L ha⁻¹ were recommended to control stem rust in Kenya (Joseph *et al.*, 2013). Chlorothalonil, Cyproconazole, Fenpropimorph, Flusilazole, Flutriafol, Prochloraz, Propiconazole and Triadimenol are fungicides used to control leaf and yellow rust in United Kingdom (England) (Cook *et al.*, 1999). As indicated in the table 3 below following commonly used fungicides were verified and used in Ethiopia.

Table 3. Major fungicides used to control rusts in Ethiopia

No	Trade names	Common names	Recommended
		Epoxiconazole+	Thiophanate-
1	Rex duo	methyl	✓ Stripe rusts
2	Natura 250EC	Tebuconazole	✓ Stripe rust
3	Bumper 25 EC	Propiconazole 25%	✓ Stem and Leaf rusts
4	Bayleton 25 WP	Triadimefon 250 g/l	✓ Stem, Leaf and Stripe rusts
5	Tilt 250 EC	Propiconazole	✓ Stem, Leaf and Stripe rust
6	Topzol 250 EC	Propiconazol 25% EC	✓ Stripe rust

Source (MoA, 2014)

Note: EC= Emulsified concentrate WP= Wettable powder

2.5.3 Host plant resistance

Genetic resistance is the main method for controlling obligate parasites. However, effective disease control requires that durable, race nonspecific resistance is incorporated into high yielding genotypes. In some areas, a shift in breeding strategies towards this durable type of resistance, based on minor additive genes, is required to avoid the ‘boom and bust’ cycles that are frequently observed. This is particularly true for areas where a single genotype is sown and the risk of mutation to new virulent races increases under selection pressure (Duveiller *et al.*, 2007). Two types of genetic resistance to rusts are known: a) seedling resistance and b) adult plant resistance. Seedling resistance, which is controlled by a single gene, is highly effective and lasts throughout the wheat life cycle (Martinez *et al.*, 2012). Virulence analysis of leaf rust (*Puccinia recondita*) showed that 10 “Lr” resistance genes (Lr1, Lr2a, Lr9, Lr15, Lr19, Lr24, Lr25, Lr26, Lr28, and Lr29) were effective on bread wheat, six on durum wheat (Lr1, Lr2a, Lr20, Lr25, Lr26, and Lr30), and six among these “Lr” genes were effective on both crop species. Red winter wheat cultivars and lines that had seedling resistance genes Lr2a, Lr9, and Lr26 combined with adult plant resistance were highly resistant to leaf rust. Cultivars and breeding lines that had seedling resistance genes Lr1, Lr10, Lr11, and Lr18 combined with adult plant resistance had moderate to low levels of leaf rust resistance in USA (Kolmer, 2004).

Known resistance genes to yellow rust (*Puccinia striiformis f.sp. tritici*) were evaluated for their effectiveness against yellow rust in Syria, Lebanon, Turkey, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, Iran, Ethiopia, and Yemen. Four resistance genes to yellow rust “Yr” were effective at all sites (Yr8, Yrcv, Yr15, and Yr17). For the diverse climatic conditions and cropping systems in Center West Asia and North Africa (CWANA), the development of multiple disease resistance is essential (Yahyaoui *et al.*, 2000). As indicated from stripe rust differential hosts, virulence was detected for Yr1, Yr2, Yr6, Yr7, Yr8, Yr9, Yr17, Yr18, YrA, Yr18+, Yr21, Yr25, Yr27, Yr27+, Yr27+Yr18, Yr28, Yr29 and Yr31 at Kulumsa field condition and at Arsi Robe field condition, virulence was detected for Yr1, Yr2, Yr6, Yr6+Yr20, Yr7, Yr9, Yr17, YrA, Yr18, Yr18+, YrA+Yr18, Yr21, Yr25, Yr27, Yr27+, Yr27+Yr18, Yr28, Yr29 and Yr31 genes during 2010 yellow rust epidemic (Worku Denbel, 2014). Yr3, Yr5, Yr10, Yr15 and YrSP in synthetic hexaploids are identified as seedling resistance genes and postulated (Sharma & Sharma, 2014). Genes Yr3a, Yr4a, Yr10, Yr17, and Yr26 confer high resistance to the tested Ethiopian isolates. Yr genes Yr6+2, Yr9+2, and Yr24 provide moderate resistance (Woubit Dawit, 2008). Bread wheat cultivars, HAR416, TUSIE (HAR 1407), BATU, DASHEN and GARA, exhibited resistance spectra. Out of the advanced bread wheat genotypes, 8.3.8 (B) and 11.6.24 were released to farmers in Ethiopia, with names KBG-01 and Meraro, during 2001 and 2005, respectively. The former was resistant to the nine races and, based on F2 segregation ratio, two complementary recessive genes, Yr9+ and Yr7 were postulated, (Ayele Badebo *et al.*, 2008).

A total of 11 stem rust resistance genes (Sr5, Sr7a, Sr7b, Sr8a, Sr9e, Sr11, Sr21, Sr27, Sr29, Sr30 and Sr37) were postulated to be present either singly or in combination in the durum and bread wheat cultivars and breeding lines in Ethiopia (Belayneh Admassu *et al.*, 2012). Differential lines which carry resistant genes Sr36, SrTmp and Sr24, were effective against the most dominant stem rust race TTKSK (UG99) whereas only Sr11, Sr24 and Sr31 were effective against the most virulence race TKTTT (Endale Hailu *et al.*, 2015). Emmer wheat and durum wheat are good source of resistance to wheat rusts (Naod Beteselassie *et al.*, 2007).

3. Conclusion and summary

The most economically important fungal diseases affecting wheat and other cereal crops globally are rust infections, which are found in many areas where wheat is grown. Wheat is susceptible to three types of rust diseases: stripe, stem, and leaf rust and hence different protection strategy following to manage them is crucial.

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